

THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FAMILY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: The family is the primary social unit where children learn values, attitudes, and behaviors that shape their personality and influence their development. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the role of the family in fostering creativity and innovation among children. This article examines the social significance of the family in the development of creative education. The study argues that the family plays a critical role in nurturing creativity by providing a supportive environment, encouraging exploration and experimentation, and fostering a sense of curiosity and wonder. The article concludes with recommendations for parents, educators, and policymakers to promote creativity in children through family-based interventions.

KEYWORDS: family, creativity, education, development, innovation

INTRODUCTION

Creativity is an essential skill for success in the 21st century. It is the ability to generate new ideas, solve problems, and think critically. Creativity is not limited to artistic expression but encompasses all aspects of human endeavor, including science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. The development of creativity begins in childhood and is influenced by a range of factors, including genetics, environment, and socialization. The family is the primary social unit where children learn values, attitudes, and behaviors that shape their personality and influence their development. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the role of the family in fostering creativity and innovation among children. This article examines the social significance of the

family in the development of creative education.

MAIN BODY

Creativity is a mental, cognitive process including flexibility, originality and giving details. It is considered an advanced mental phenomenon in which the individual deals with situations, experiences and problems in a creative way or by putting forward a collection of solutions to get one good solution. Gilford's definition of creativity that is mentioned in Obeid's (2000) is "the readiness characteristics that include the freedom and flexibility of thinking, originality and sensitivity to problems, redefining the problem and clarifying it by details", Abu Jadu (2004) considered creativity as a form of leadership in which the creator practices a personal clear influence on others. The creative environment is the atmosphere that includes the situations and condition, that simplify the creativity. The researchers point out that creativity is a compound mental purposeful activity guiding a strong desire in searching for solutions or reaching original results that haven't been known before.

Each person has different activities and talents but the ways in which those activities and talents are displayed are different. (creativity is the only thing an individual can do effectively to establish his / her own presence .The modern world is concerned with the creators in order to give solutions for the human problems, such as the alternative energy ,fighting, current diseases and war and peace. The elements of creative schools are represented by the creative teacher , students and administration .The creative teacher and administration are the ones who could light up the creative energy of the students and reveal the individual differences for them. The classroom should be attractive and sunny not as wood store. Childhood has become the main concern for parents, educators and thinkers because of its importance as the basic stage in building up the human being. So, each life experience that is offered for children contributes in preparing them in the best way. In fact, the family plays a big role in developing the children's

abilities in dealing with problems in creativity. Those children are born with the seed of creativity and the family works on caring such creativity or vanishing it. Islamic education has given a high rank for childhood as being the most influential on the future of individuals and groups. The parents should be highly aware of their responsibility in raising their children correctly mentally, psychologically, socially and in having faith, as well. In addition, having consideration for the external influences on the children.

Developing the children's creativity is possible because each child has a heaven creativity ability that could be enhanced and refined by the way of bringing up (Oweis, 2003), Al Zahrani(2003:337) pointed out that" the ability of creativity is not exclusive for the elite, but it is available for all individuals and parents could affect their children positively".

The family provides a supportive environment for children to explore their interests and talents. Parents who encourage their children to pursue their passions and interests create an environment that fosters creativity. Children who are allowed to explore their interests without fear of failure are more likely to develop a sense of curiosity and wonder that fuels creative thinking. Parents can also provide resources such as books, materials, and tools that enable their children to experiment and create.

The family also plays a critical role in encouraging exploration and experimentation. Children who are allowed to explore their environment and try new things are more likely to develop a sense of independence and self-confidence that fosters creativity. Parents who provide opportunities for their children to experiment with different ideas and approaches create an environment that encourages creative thinking.

Fostering a sense of curiosity and wonder is another important aspect of the family's role in nurturing creativity. Children who are encouraged to ask questions, seek answers, and explore their environment are more likely to develop

a sense of wonder that fuels creative thinking. Parents who model curiosity and wonder in their own lives create an environment that fosters creativity.

The family faces a real challenge in raising the creative child and in dealing with the gifted one by feeding his continuous desire for knowledge and exploring the unknown. Because of the great necessity for creativity at this time, it is compulsory for school and family to contribute in developing creativity for children.

Therefore, this study is to offer awareness for teachers about the importance of creativity and how to contribute in developing their students' creativity to produce new and fruitful thoughts.

CONCLUSION:

The family is a critical social unit in the development of creative education. Parents who provide a supportive environment, encourage exploration and experimentation, and foster a sense of curiosity and wonder create an environment that nurtures creativity. Educators and policymakers can promote creativity in children by supporting family-based interventions that encourage parents to provide resources, opportunities, and modeling that foster creativity. The development of creativity is essential for success in the 21st century, and the family plays a critical role in its development.

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